

"Rewiring the role of hydrogen sulphide an investigation in neurodegenerative disorders"

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The positive benefits of hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) were well known at the time of ancient Greece. Depending on the microbiota and oxygen content, sulphur springs contain H₂S with anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and vasodilatory properties. Epidemiological studies also report that a diet rich in sulphur species is associated with longevity. However, by definition, H₂S is a toxic gas that causes acute and chronic side effects.

Since the late 1990s, H₂S has emerged as the third endogenous and bioactive "gasotransmitter", in addition to nitric oxide and carbon monoxide, contributing to numerous physiological functions in mammalian systems. Especially in the central nervous system (CNS), it acts as a cell-signalling factor to maintain balanced amounts of antioxidants and combat reactive oxygen species (ROS). However, H₂S exhibits a double biological action switching from being a neuromodulator at low concentrations (nanomolar, low micromolar) to a neurotoxic agent when present at harmful levels (mid to high micromolar). A variety of human diseases were indeed shown to be associated with pathologically high or low H₂S levels such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, Huntington's, Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and, interestingly, Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS). In ALS, toxic H₂S levels promote cell death, inhibit mitochondrial function and, in turn, alter calcium homeostasis, accumulating ROS.

Furthermore, H₂S signaling via sulfhydration affects the activity of target proteins in determining susceptibility to oxidative damage and neurodegeneration, as in MS.

Much progress has been made, but many studies are still needed to understand the role and significance of H₂S-mediated redox imbalance as a contributing factor to neurodegenerative diseases.